

Reduction of allergenic mite populations in dog and cat sleeping areas using an attractive textile trap

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Abstract

The objective of this laboratory study was to evaluate the ability of an attractive textile trap, followed by removal and washing of this textile, to reduce populations of allergenic mites present in supports simulating dog and cat sleeping areas. The measured criteria were the transfer of mites to the attractive textile trap and the decrease in the number of mites remaining in the infested support after application of the protocol.

Two complementary experimental approaches were used. First, a repeated-use experiment was performed on small mattresses experimentally infested with *Dermatophagoides* spp. mites. The small mattresses were maintained under controlled conditions, treated weekly and analysed for four weeks. The mattress-type support and the textile trap were aspirated separately, and the collected material was retained on filters before mite counting. A parallel control experiment was performed with a textile trap impregnated with water instead of the attractive commercial formulation.

Results: the residual mite population in the treated group decreased to 15,6 % of the initial population after one week, 5,0 % after two weeks, 2,7 % after three weeks and 1,2 % after four weeks. In the water-treated control, the residual population decreased to 77,8 %, 52,3 %, 52,1 % and 38,3 % of the initial population at the same times.

Second, experiments were performed on infested cushions to evaluate the transfer of mites from the cushion to an attractive textile trap after a single treatment. These trials included two mite species, *Dermatophagoides* spp. and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*.

Results: 64,1 +/- 6,0 % of *Dermatophagoides* spp. and 73,9 +/- 10,2 % of *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* were collected on the textile treated with the attractive formulation, compared with respectively 32,5 +/- 2,2 % and 41,9 +/- 4,2 % in the water-treated control.

Exploratory Welch comparisons, based on three replicate cushions per treatment condition, indicated statistically higher collection of mites in the textile with the attractive protocol than with the water control for *Dermatophagoides* spp. (mean difference: 31,6 percentage points; $p = 0,006$) and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* (mean difference: 32,0 percentage points; $p = 0,020$).

These results show that, under the laboratory conditions tested, the protocol based on a textile trap treated with an attractive formulation was associated with increased collection of mites.

Keywords: allergenic mites; *Dermatophagoides*; *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*; textile treated with attractant; removable textile; dog basket; cat basket; laboratory study

1. Introduction

Textile and padded sleeping areas used by dogs and cats can retain dust, skin debris and organic matter, and may therefore provide microhabitats in which mites can be present. The present study focuses on two groups of allergenic mites that are relevant to these environments: dust mites of the genus *Dermatophagoides* and storage mites of the genus *Tyrophagus*.

Dermatophagoides spp. are common domestic mites associated with indoor dust, mattresses, bedding and other textile environments. Their biology, taxonomy and occurrence in domestic environments have been extensively described in the dust mite literature [1].

Tyrophagus putrescentiae is a storage mite associated with stored products, food-related environments and other human-associated habitats [2]. Storage mites are also relevant in veterinary allergology, as sensitisation to *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* has been evaluated by intradermal testing in dogs with atopic dermatitis [3,4].

Cross-reactivity between dust mites and storage mites has been reported, supporting the practical relevance of considering both groups when evaluating strategies aimed at reducing mite exposure in the resting environments of dogs and cats [5].

Environmental control of mites has also been investigated in sensitised dogs. Clinical studies evaluating treatment of the domestic environment have reported improvement in clinical signs in some animals, supporting the practical interest of strategies designed to reduce exposure to mites in dogs' sleeping areas [6].

2. Objective

The objective of the present laboratory study was to evaluate whether an attractive removable textile trap could reduce the number of allergenic mites present in supports simulating dog and cat sleeping areas.

The measured criteria were the number of mites remaining in the simulated sleeping support and the number of mites collected from the treated textile trap.

The specific objectives were: first, to measure the progressive reduction of *Dermatophagoides* spp. remaining in mattress-type supports after repeated weekly use of the protocol; second, to compare this reduction with a water-treated control; and third, to evaluate, in a complementary one-use model, the transfer of *Dermatophagoides* spp. and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* from infested cushions to a treated removable textile trap after a single treatment.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Tested product

The tested product was a commercial attractive formulation used according to its intended use protocol. The experimental data reported here were generated during laboratory experiments conducted by the author. The experimental protocol, the mite collection method, the exposure conditions, the repetition

scheme and the quantitative results are described. For reasons of industrial confidentiality, the exact formulation and concentrations are not disclosed in this manuscript.

3.2. Experimental datasets

Dataset	Target mites	Experimental support	Main criterion
Repeated-use experiment	<i>Dermatophagoides</i> spp.	Small mattress-type supports, 1535 cm ²	Residual mite population after four weekly applications of a textile + attractant protocol
One-use experiment	<i>Dermatophagoides</i> spp. and <i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i>	Infested cushions placed in plastic dog baskets	Mites collected on the removable textile after one treatment and one hour of exposure

Table 1. Experimental data included in the main analysis.

3.3. Repeated-use experiment with *Dermatophagoides* spp.

Small mattress-type supports were used to simulate textile sleeping areas. Twelve mattresses were experimentally infested with *Dermatophagoides* spp. mites. Each mattress had a surface area of 1535 cm².

The mattresses were maintained under controlled laboratory conditions at 50 % relative humidity and 20 deg C. Protein-based food was provided to the mites. The mean initial infestation was 241 +/- 74 mites per mattress.

At week 0, the mites were introduced into the mattresses. The commercial protocol was then applied each week. The application consisted of six sprays, corresponding to 4,62 ml of product per mattress surface.

Direct counting at the time of infestation was not used, because it would have disturbed or injured the mites. The mite numbers were therefore estimated after treatment. The mattress and the removable textile were aspirated separately. The collected material was retained on a filter, then the mites were counted.

Recorded variables. M = number of mites collected in the mattress-type support; I = number of mites collected in the removable textile; Tot = total number of mites collected in the mattress plus the textile; percentage collection in textile = $I / Tot \times 100$.

At week 1, the protocol was applied to the 12 mattresses. Three mattresses were fully analysed by counting the mites in the mattress and in the textile, while the number of mites present in the textile alone was measured for the remaining nine mattresses. At weeks 2, 3 and 4, the same logic was applied to the remaining mattresses. This experimental design made it possible to follow the evolution of mite collection over repeated weekly applications.

A parallel control experiment was performed with water instead of the commercial formulation. The same methodology was applied to another set of 12 mattresses.

3.4. One-use experiment with *Dermatophagoides* spp. and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*

Complementary one-use experiments were performed on cushions placed in plastic dog baskets. The cushions measured 43 x 30 x 6 cm and were infested with live mites. The test included *Dermatophagoides* spp and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*.

After infestation, the mites were left in place for 15 hours. A dark 100 % cotton towel measuring 43 x 30 cm was then placed on the cushion. The towel was treated with the attractive formulation and left in place for 1 hour. After treatment, the towel and the cushion were aspirated separately, and the dust samples were analysed under a microscope to determine the number of mites collected in the towel and in the cushion.

The one-use experiment compared the textile + attractant protocol, a textile + water control and a dry textile control. Three replicate cushions were used per treatment condition. The criterion studied was the percentage of mites collected on the removable textile.

3.5. Statistical analysis

The results are presented descriptively as means and standard deviations. For the one-use experiment, exploratory comparisons between the textile + attractant protocol and each control were calculated using two-sample Welch t-tests, from the reported means, standard deviations and numbers of replicates (n = 3 per treatment condition). Mean differences are reported in percentage points with 95 % confidence intervals. As the sample size was small and percentages are bounded variables, these inferential statistics are exploratory and were not adjusted for multiple comparisons.

4. Results

4.1. Repeated-use experiment with *Dermatophagoides* spp.

The repeated-use protocol resulted in a progressive reduction in the number of mites remaining in the mattress-type supports.

The water-treated control also showed a reduction over time, but this reduction was slower and less marked. Compared with the water-treated control, the textile + attractant protocol resulted in a faster and greater descriptive reduction in the number of mites remaining in the mattress-type supports.

Time	n fully analysed	Residual population: textile + attractant	Reduction: textile + attractant	Residual population: textile + water	Reduction: textile + water
Week 1	3	15,6 %	84,4 %	77,8 %	22,2 %
Week 2	3	5,0 %	95,0 %	52,3 %	47,7 %
Week 3	3	2,7 %	97,3 %	52,1 %	47,9 %
Week 4	3	1,2 %	98,8 %	38,3 %	61,7 %

Table 2. Residual population of *Dermatophagoides* spp. over four weekly applications. n fully analysed refers to the supports for which both the mattress and textile compartments were counted at the corresponding time.

Figure 1. Evolution of the residual population of *Dermatophagoides* spp. in the mattress-type supports over four weeks. Values are expressed as a percentage of the initial population.

4.2. One-use experiment with *Dermatophagoides* spp. and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*

In the one-use experiment, the textile + attractant protocol increased the proportion of mites collected in the removable textile compared with the textile + water and dry textile controls.

Treatment	<i>Dermatophagoides</i> spp. (% of mites collected in the textile)	<i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i> (% of mites collected in the textile)
Textile + attractive formulation	64,1 +/- 6,0 %	73,9 +/- 10,2 %
Textile + water	32,5 +/- 2,2 %	41,9 +/- 4,2 %
Dry textile	15,0 +/- 5,9 %	25,9 +/- 5,6 %

Table 3. Mites collected in the removable textile after one treatment followed by one hour of exposure. Values are means +/- standard deviations.

Figure 2. Collection of *Dermatophagoides spp.* and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* on the removable textile in the one-use experiment. Error bars indicate standard deviations.

4.3. Exploratory statistical comparison of the one-use experiment

The textile + attractant protocol was compared with the textile + water and dry textile controls in the one-use experiment. The values below are exploratory Welch comparisons calculated from the means and standard deviations by treatment, with three replicate cushions per treatment condition.

Species	Comparison	Mean difference (percentage points)	95 % CI	p value
<i>Dermatophagoides spp.</i>	Textile + attractant vs textile + water	31,6	18,5 to 44,7	0,006
<i>Dermatophagoides spp.</i>	Textile + attractant vs dry textile	49,1	35,6 to 62,6	0,001
<i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i>	Textile + attractant vs textile + water	32,0	10,2 to 53,8	0,020
<i>Tyrophagus putrescentiae</i>	Textile + attractant vs dry textile	48,0	27,0 to 69,0	0,005

Table 4. Exploratory Welch comparisons for mite collection on the removable textile in the one-use experiment. CI = confidence interval. The analyses are based on n = 3 replicate cushions per treatment condition and should be interpreted with caution.

5. Discussion

This laboratory study documents the collection of allergenic mites from supports simulating dog and cat sleeping areas by means of a removable textile treated with an attractive formulation.

The repeated-use experiment shows a progressive reduction of *Dermatophagoides* spp. remaining in the mattress-type supports over four weeks. The residual mite population decreased from 100 % at the beginning of the experiment to 15,6 % after one week, 5,0 % after two weeks, 2,7 % after three weeks and 1,2 % after four weeks.

The water-treated control also showed a reduction, but this reduction was lower at each time. This indicates that part of the mite population may decrease or be removed by handling, placement of the textile, collection by aspiration or environmental conditions, while the protocol combining a removable textile and an attractive formulation produced a greater descriptive reduction under the tested conditions.

The complementary one-use experiment extends the observation to *Tyrophagus putrescentiae*. In this experiment, after one treatment and 1 hour of exposure, 73,9 % of *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* were collected on the textile treated with the attractive formulation, compared with 41,9 % in the textile + water control and 25,9 % in the dry textile control. The exploratory Welch comparisons indicated higher collection with the textile + attractant protocol than with the water and dry controls, but these statistics should be interpreted with caution, because only three replicate cushions were available per treatment condition.

The results should not be interpreted as an effect of the textile alone. The textile + water and dry textile controls show that a textile support can collect part of the mites, but the collection observed with the textile + attractant protocol was higher. The central observation is therefore the technical effect of the association between a textile support and an attractive formulation, and not the textile in isolation.

6. Limitations

The supports used in the experiments were simplified laboratory models. They simulate dog or cat sleeping areas, but do not reproduce the full variability of real baskets, cushions, blankets or domestic conditions.

The exact formulation and concentrations of the commercial product are not disclosed for reasons of industrial confidentiality. This limits full independent reproducibility of the formulation; the reproducible elements are the application protocol, the mite collection method and the measured results.

The study does not evaluate all possible textile types, environmental conditions, infestation levels or mite species.

Allergen concentrations were not measured. The statistical analyses are exploratory because of the small sample size. For the one-use experiment, the inferential comparisons were calculated from summary statistics by treatment with $n = 3$ per group.

No formal inferential statistics were applied to the repeated-use experiment, because each time point was based on a small destructive subsample.

7. Conclusion

Under controlled laboratory conditions, the protocol combining a removable textile and an attractive formulation was associated with collection of allergenic mites from supports simulating dog and cat sleeping areas.

In the repeated-use experiment conducted with *Dermatophagoides* spp., the residual mite population in the mattress-type supports decreased to 5,0 % of the initial population after two weekly applications and to 1,2 % after four weekly applications.

In the complementary one-use experiments, *Dermatophagoides* spp. and *Tyrophagus putrescentiae* were both collected on the treated removable textile after a single exposure, with higher collection than with the textile + water and dry textile controls.

These results document the technical ability of the textile + attractant protocol to increase mite collection on a removable support under the laboratory conditions tested. They should not be interpreted as evidence of allergen reduction or clinical benefit.

8. Conflict of interest statement

Anne-Catherine Mailleux is associated with the development and commercialization of the tested product. This relationship is declared for transparency.

9. Author contribution statement

Anne-Catherine Mailleux designed the study, supervised the experiments, analysed the results and prepared the manuscript.

10. References

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